

Supplementary Material

Prompt Literacy and Software Quality: A Cross-Cultural Study on the Impact of Prompt Engineering Training on Generative AI Use by Undergraduate Students

This document contains the instruments referenced in the paper. It is intended to support independent assessment and replication. Numeric parameters marked “indicative” are finalized when the study materials are built.

S1. The STAR-Prompting Framework (extended description)

STAR-Prompting adapts the STAR method (Situation, Task, Action, Result), originally used in human-resources behavioral interviews, into a prompt-engineering technique. Each prompt is organized along four dimensions:

- **Situation.** Problem context and constraints.
- **Task.** The objective to accomplish.
- **Action.** Specific instructions for the AI.
- **Result.** The expected output format.

Rather than exposing these labels to the user, the technique renders them as a single continuous natural-language instruction. In the training module, non-programmers are taught to build prompts following the template:

“You are... (Situation); You need to... (Task); Do... (Action); As a result, I want... (Result).”

Provenance and level of evidence. The framework was introduced by Gonçalves et al. [14] as a proof of concept in the defense-and-security domain, comparing free-form and STAR-structured prompts across four large language models (Gemini Flash 2.0, Llama 3.3 70B, GPT-4o-mini, Claude 3.5 Sonnet). That initial evaluation was qualitative and based on a small prompt set, without a scored rubric, multiple raters, or statistical testing. Because the technique structures the reasoning of the prompt independently of subject matter, it is in principle domain-agnostic. The present study tests this generality by transposing it from a specialized technical domain to everyday tasks performed by non-technical users, and supplies the controlled, quantitative evaluation, scored rubric, two independent raters, and statistical analysis, that the original proof of concept did not include.

S2. Generic Quality Rubric (0–3)

Applied to **Correctness** and **Completeness** by two independent raters, with inter-rater agreement measured by Cohen’s Kappa. **Functionality** is measured separately by functional testing (pass / partial / fail) and is not rated on this rubric, providing an objective anchor independent of rater judgement.

Correctness. Does the output match expected results?

Score	Descriptor
0	Incorrect. The artifact produces wrong or unrelated results; the core logic is absent or mistaken.

Score	Descriptor
1	Largely incorrect. The artifact addresses the task but contains errors that compromise the main result (e.g., wrong formula, incorrect output on most test cases).
2	Largely correct. The artifact produces the expected result on most test cases, with minor errors or untreated edge cases.
3	Correct. The artifact produces the expected result on all defined test cases, including edge cases.

Completeness — does it meet all task requirements?

Score	Descriptor
0	Absent. The artifact ignores most stated task requirements.
1	Partial. The artifact meets some requirements but omits mandatory components.
2	Substantial. The artifact meets all mandatory requirements, missing only optional or secondary elements.
3	Full. The artifact meets all mandatory and secondary requirements defined in the task acceptance grid.

S3. Task Bank and Acceptance Grid

Each task is described to participants in natural language and requires no programming knowledge. For each task we specify the mandatory and secondary requirements and how Correctness and Completeness are determined against fixed test cases prepared in advance. The numeric parameters below (number of test cases, number of reviews) are indicative and finalized when the materials are built.

Task 1 - BMI calculator

Statement: “Create a calculator that takes a person’s weight (kg) and height (m) and reports their Body Mass Index (BMI) and the corresponding category (underweight, normal, overweight, obese).”

- **Test cases:** a fixed set of 5 (weight, height) pairs covering each category, plus 1 edge case at a category boundary (e.g., BMI = 25.0).
- **Mandatory:** (a) BMI computed as $\text{weight}/\text{height}^2$; (b) correct classification into the four categories; (c) accepts numeric input.
- **Secondary:** validation of invalid input (text, zero, negative).
- **Correctness:** proportion of test cases with correct BMI and category.
- **Completeness:** presence of mandatory and secondary requirements.

Task 2 - Monthly expenses spreadsheet by category

Statement: “Create a spreadsheet that, from a list of expenses with amount and category, automatically computes the total spent per category and the overall monthly total.”

- **Provided data:** a fixed set of ~15 entries (amount + category) whose per-category and overall totals are known to the researcher (answer key).

- **Mandatory:** (a) correct per-category sums; (b) correct overall total; (c) totals update when a value is changed.
- **Secondary:** currency formatting; sorting or display by category.
- **Correctness:** per-category and overall totals match the answer key.
- **Completeness:** mandatory and secondary requirements present.

Task 3 - Multiple-choice quiz with final score

Statement: “Create a multiple-choice quiz with at least 5 questions that, at the end, shows the user’s score (number of correct answers).”

- **Mandatory:** (a) at least 5 questions with alternatives; (b) records the selected answer; (c) correctly computes and displays the number of correct answers.
- **Secondary:** per-question feedback (correct/incorrect); quiz restart.
- **Correctness:** final score matches the answers given in a fixed test script (e.g., 3 correct out of 5 displays 3).
- **Completeness:** mandatory and secondary requirements present.

Task 4 - Summarize customer reviews

Statement: “From a list of customer reviews, generate a summary of the main positive and negative points mentioned.”

- **Provided data:** a fixed set of reviews (e.g., 15) catalogued in advance by the researcher, defining the answer key of distinct positive points (P1...Pn) and negative points (N1...Nm) present in the set.
- **Correctness (recall/precision against the key):** proportion of key points correctly captured (recall) and proportion of the points listed by the student that actually occur in the set, without fabrication or hallucination (precision), mapped to the 0–3 scale by recall/precision bands defined a priori.
- **Completeness:** covers both positive and negative points, including the most frequent points in the set.
- **Limitation note:** this task is more subjective than the others; it is therefore evaluated against a fixed answer key, inter-rater agreement (Cohen’s Kappa) is reported with reinforced attention for this task, and its results are interpreted with additional caution.

Task 5 - Currency converter (local / USD / EUR)

Statement: “Create a converter that converts an amount between the local currency (BRL in Brazil, USD in the United States), the US Dollar, and the Euro, using provided exchange rates.”

- **Provided data:** fixed exchange rates supplied to the participant (so the task does not depend on live quotes), plus a set of 5 test amounts.
- **Mandatory:** (a) correct conversion between the three currencies using the provided rates; (b) accepts an amount and a conversion direction.
- **Secondary:** rounding to two decimals; easy switching of source/target currency.
- **Correctness:** results match the expected calculation at the provided rates.
- **Completeness:** mandatory and secondary requirements present.

S4. Recall/Precision Bands for Task 4 (to be finalized)

Mapping of recall/precision to the 0–3 Correctness scale for Task 4, defined a priori before rating begins. Fill in the exact bands when the review key is built; the structure below is illustrative.

Score	Recall	Precision
3	≥ 0.80	≥ 0.80
2	0.60–0.79	≥ 0.70
1	0.40–0.59	≥ 0.50
0	< 0.40	< 0.50

S5. Contents of the full replication package (to be uploaded)

- The asynchronous prompt-engineering training module (four blocks) and the attention-control module.
- The five task statements as presented to participants, in Portuguese (BR cohort) and English (US cohort).
- The complete answer keys and fixed test cases for Tasks 1, 2, 3, 5, and the review key for Task 4.
- The demographic questionnaire, the 5-question comprehension quiz, and the perception questionnaire (confidence, satisfaction).
- Anonymized data and analysis scripts (R / Python) after data collection.